

Metallogeny of the Dinarides in the frame of the Wilson cycle

Ladislav A. Palinkaš¹, Sabina S. Palinkaš², Sibila Borojević Šoštarić¹, Franjo Šumanovac¹

¹ University of Zagreb, Faculty of Mining, Geology and Petroleum Engineering, Pierottijeva 6, HR-10.000 Zagreb; e-mails: ladislav.palinkas@geol.pmf.hr; sibila.borojevic-sostaric@rgn.unizg.hr; franjo.sumanovac@rgn.unizg.hr

² The Antarctic University of Norway, Department of Geosciences, Tromsø, Norway; e-mail: sabina.s.palinkas@uit.no

The Dinaridic metallogenic province is a part of the Alpine–Himalayan orogenic system, developed as a result of opening and closure of the Neo-Tethys Ocean by convergence of the African and Eurasian plates. The northern boundary of the Dinarides is related to the northern African margin (Adria–Apulia). The Tisia mega-unit, a small continental block, positioned between the Dinarides and the Carpathians, is genetically related to the South Eurasian margin.

The geology of the Dinarides is constrained by the Alpine Wilson cycle. The major stages of the cycle are: (a) Permian early intra-continental rifting; (b) Triassic advanced rifting; (c) Jurassic oceanization; (d) Cretaceous subduction; (e) Paleogene collision; and (f) Neogene post-collision and extension followed by orogenic collapse. Each stage creates characteristic ore deposits related to the specific geological environments.

Stage (a) bears hydrothermal siderite-barite-polysulphide deposits, epigenetic sedimentary uranium deposits, red bed-type, sabkha-type copper and barite deposits and evaporites. Stage (b) favored SEDEX and hydrothermal iron-polysulphide-barite-mercury and MVT deposits. Stage (c) developed chromites, asbestos, talc and magnesite deposits. The spatial position of stage (d) remains poorly constrained.

The Southern Tisia unit might be a possible candidate for the Neo-Tethyan active continental margin with the Cretaceous subduction zone positioned beneath. Absence of voluminous subduction-related magmatism and mineral deposits, however, favors subduction within the Vardar zone (the easternmost Dinarides), adjoined to the Serbo-Macedonian ensialic terrain with its large porphyry-Cu deposits. Stage (e) was a prelude to the prolific phase (f) with its numerous hydrothermal Pb, Zn and Sb deposits that mostly occur in the western Vardar Zone.

The presentation deals with metallogenic characteristics of the Dinarides, based on recently-gained knowledge on the regional geology, petrology and genesis of mineral deposits. Establishment of the plate tectonic model several decades ago greatly contributed to an integrated interpretation of ore deposit genesis. In turn, basic research in the field of ore genesis generated new data that can be used to improve the plate tectonic model.

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